

Video Copywriting of Pempek Cek Yati

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ABSTRACT: This study discusses the video copywriting process of Pempek Cek Yati using the modified Research and Development (R&D) method by Sukmadinata (2019). The purpose of this study was to outline the steps involved in creating the video copywriting, focusing on three stages: (1) Preliminary study; (2) Model Development; and (3) Product Drafting. There were seven experts of scriptwriting, English, and video editing participated in providing comments and suggestions chosen by purposive sampling. The data were collected by both observation, and interviews, and analyzed through a coding analysis by (Gale, Heath, Cameron, Rashid, & Redwood, 2013 and Furber, 2010). The findings revealed some areas needing improvement, as identified by each expert. The language experts suggested fixing some grammatical error in some parts of ad copy. The video experts suggested revising some parts of video such as changing the filter, adding the logo of institution, the size of subtitle, and adding contact person information. This video copywriting is expected to provide detailed information of Pempek Cek Yati.

Keywords: *Copy Writing, Culinary Tourism, Pempek Cek Yati, Research and Development, Video*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism involves people traveling for pleasure, seeking new experiences and knowledge.

Culinary tourism, a growing trend, focuses on food as an expression of culture and identity (Wijaya, 2019). Travelers increasingly explore destinations for culinary delights, including traditional dishes.

In South Sumatra, culinary tourism thrives, prominently featuring Pempek from Palembang City. Pempek, especially popular at places like Pasar 26, Pasar 16, and others, is a highlight for tourists visiting Palembang. Pempek Cek Yati, located on Sultan Muhammad Mansyur Street, stands out among local establishments but remains relatively unknown beyond Palembang.

To expand its reach, promoting Pempek Cek Yati through various media channels, such as online articles, blogs, and videos, is crucial. Videos are particularly effective due to their visual and engaging nature, offering viewers a vivid portrayal and facilitating better retention of information.

Promotional videos serve as powerful tools for introducing products or brands (Indy et al., 2021). They efficiently convey information and capture viewer attention, often incorporating copywriting techniques to influence and engage the audience effectively. Effective copywriting in promotional videos aims to evoke responses from viewers by presenting compelling visuals and messages that resonate.

Copywriting involves crafting persuasive marketing materials that spur action, like purchasing, clicking, donating, or scheduling (American Writers and Artistic Institute, 2020). It's about creating compelling ads or promotions for products, emphasizing their benefits to encourage actions such as subscribing or purchasing (Riadi, 2020; Nayoan, 2021).

Based on Romeltea (2016), there are various linguistic styles commonly used in copywriting. The first one is explorative which explores product advantages concisely to convince the audience. Second is denotative which uses clear, unambiguous language to convey direct meanings. Next is narrative which presents the product as a story, engaging readers. Fourth is imaginative which includes creative language while maintaining product accuracy. Fifth is argumentative which influences with logical arguments and evidence. Sixth is informative which provides detailed product information. Lastly is persuasive which urges immediate action from the audience. Understanding these styles is crucial for effective copywriting (Romeltea, 2016), helping copywriters tailor advertisements to effectively convey messages.

In order to do a good copywriting, Rieck (2008) gives five steps that need to do which are: 1. Prepare: Gather information through client discussions, focusing on product/service descriptions, customer benefits, pricing, specifications, history, target audience, and testimonials. 2. Organize: Structure gathered information to shape the copywriting process, refining ideas through note-taking and outlining. 3. Write: Begin crafting the copy by prioritizing elements like headlines, subheads (emphasizing benefits in active voice), body content (expanded from

headlines), and a clear closing. 4. Edit: Refine the copy for clarity and conciseness, ensuring every word contributes effectively to the message. 5. Review: Set aside the copy, gather feedback from impartial parties, address any issues identified, and consider alternative approaches. These steps are essential for creating effective copywriting that communicates messages clearly and persuasively.

This study uses multiple frameworks in copywriting analysis to offer a comprehensive evaluation compared to a single framework, providing diverse perspectives on elements like persuasiveness, emotional appeal, and linguistic structure (Gale et al., 2013). This approach integrates creative and strategic aspects, enhancing the effectiveness of the final product by identifying strengths and weaknesses across different dimensions. Specific frameworks may be more suitable for different types of content or audiences, ensuring a tailored analysis that considers all relevant factors. By avoiding reliance on a single framework, biases are minimized, and a more balanced assessment can inform strategic decisions in advertising. Furthermore, employing varied frameworks expands understanding of copywriting principles and enhances professional skills over time (Oshima & Hogue, 2006). This study utilized multiple frameworks to refine copywriting quality and adapt content effectively for advertising purposes, emphasizing systematic organization and clear communication of persuasive ideas throughout the text.

The basic framework of text organization ensures well-structured essays with clear introductions, coherent body paragraphs, and credible evidence integration (Oshima & Hogue, 2006). This study also utilized the AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) model, introduced by Elias St. Elmo Lewis in 1898, to guide marketing efforts (Techtarget, 2017; Rofiq et al., 2012; Kotler & Keller, 2009). AIDA delineates four stages—Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action—that are crucial in effective advertising. It aims to capture attention, stimulate interest, create desire, and prompt consumer action, influencing purchasing decisions (Kotler & Keller, 2012).

By understanding and applying the AIDA model, marketers can systematically craft persuasive messages that resonate with their target audience and encourage desired actions. This process starts with attracting attention through effective promotion, followed by cultivating consumer interest and desire, ultimately leading to a decision to purchase or engage with the product or service offered.

Pempek Cek Yati, a culinary hotspot in Palembang City located at Jalan Simpang Poltek, Lebak Keranji, Bukit Lama, was founded by Mrs. Hayati in 2007. The name "Cek" is a local term meaning "older sister." Known for its traditional Palembang dishes like pempek lenjer, pempek telur, and otak-otak, it expanded with a branch in Sukabangun by 2020. Operating daily from 09:00 to 21:00, the restaurant offers a serene ambiance with a nearby garden.

Therefore, this study focuses on developing a promotional video for Pempek Cek Yati, applying the AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) formula and ensuring linguistic accuracy in the script. By crafting an engaging video copy, this research aims to enhance awareness of Pempek Cek Yati as a culinary tourism destination in Palembang.

METHOD

This study utilized descriptive qualitative research, which aims to comprehensively understand human or social phenomena through detailed narratives gathered from informants in natural settings (Walidin, Saifullah, & Tabrani, 2015). Qualitative research, inherently descriptive and employing inductive analysis, emphasizes understanding processes and meanings from the subjects' perspectives (Fadli, 2021). This method systematically captures factual overviews of phenomena without experimental manipulation, ensuring results align with real-world conditions.

The research followed a modified Research and Development (R&D) approach by Sukmadinata (2019), comprising preliminary study, model development, and final product

testing. This methodology, condensed into ten steps including research planning, prototype creation, field testing, and iterative refinement, accommodated constraints of time, cost, and resources encountered during the study.

Data Collection

This study uses participant observation and interviews. Participant observation, involving researchers directly in a social context (Lofland et al., 2022), aims to gather rich qualitative data by immersing in the group's activities and interactions. This method offers an insider's view of beliefs, values, and practices, enabling deep understanding of social contexts and participants' perspectives. The observation, conducted on 8 June 2023 for 1 hour at Pempek Cek Yati, facilitated natural exploration of social phenomena and behaviors through direct experience.

Furthermore, interview type for this study is semi-structured interview. The semi-structured interviews are frequently used to gather data, and the effectiveness of the interview guide has a significant impact on the results of the research (Kallio et al., 2016). As this research needed three kinds of expert, namely: Scriptwriting, English, and video editing, the interview questions were developed for three of them.

On June 9, 2023, the writer interviewed the owner of Pempek Cek Yati for 45 minutes at the restaurant. The interview covered 6 topics: location, operational hours, menu variants, favorite menu item, product strengths, and delivery details. It was recorded and documented in an interview journal with participant validation.

In developing the product, the writer interviewed experts in scriptwriting, English, and video editing at their homes and State Polytechnic of Sriwijaya. Interview questions for each expertise: scriptwriting (based on Azar & Hagen, 1999), English (based on Ellis, 2021), and video editing (based on Sreepoorna, 2020). Three questions covered grammar, punctuation, and diction for scriptwriting and English, while video editing questions (five in total) addressed video content,

type, size, information, and content specifics. Interviews were recorded on a smartphone and documented in an interview journal with participant validation.

Data Analysis

To analyze the observation data, the data involved careful and systematic examination and iterative review and reflection of observations to identify patterns, themes, and recurring behaviors or events from field notes. The analysis included categorizing, coding, and organizing data to identify key insights and concepts and produce meaningful interpretations.

For interview data, this study followed coding analysis steps outlined by Gale et al. (2013). Initially, interviews were transcribed to text format for easier handling. Data cleaning involved removing irrelevant information and correcting transcription errors. Categories were then assigned to identify main themes emerging from interviews and observations. This process organized and simplified the data, allowing for deeper exploration of relationships between codes and themes. Themes were developed to interpret and analyze the data, revealing connections and explanations within and across themes. The first draft followed a text structure proposed by Oshima & Hogue (2006), comprising an opening with background, theme, hook, and thesis, elaborated in the body, and concluded in the closing. The final product adhered to the AIDA Formula by Kotler & Keller (2009), aiming to grab attention, generate interest, create desire, and prompt action. These frameworks guided the development of the video copy at various stages.

Model Development

The second stage, model development, demonstrated the product's quality through limited and extensive testing involving experts (Sukmadinata, 2019). The process included:

1. Limited Testing: Initially, the writer showed the Bahasa Indonesia script to Ms. Dea Destriana, manager at Serangkai Creative Agency, for feedback on diction and concept. After revisions based on her suggestions, the script was translated and reviewed by Ms. Pratiwi Lestari,

M.Pd, an English teacher, for grammar and content.

2. Wider Testing: This phase involved improving the product based on feedback from a larger group. Five participants provided insights: Mr. Rio Pratama, a video editor and designer, reviewed the video's overall design; Fadira Tiara Ramadhani commented on subtitle size; Rizka Nabila and Lidya Ferliana suggested subtitle color and additional information about Pempek Cek Yati's contact details, respectively; and Mr. Ardiansyah offered design recommendations. The video underwent adjustments to incorporate all feedback from participants, enhancing its appeal and effectiveness.

Final Product

This step was the final step of the product's development. It included testing and distribution of the finished product. Due to time constraints, financial constraints, and legal considerations, the writer chose not to test the product or distribute it. Sukmadinata (2019) added that research and development might be suspended till the final draft without product testing while writing a final project for undergraduate students. Because of this, the writer halted production and used the version from wider testing as the final product of this final report.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this research, findings were categorized into three phases: preliminary study, model development, and final product. Data collection involved participant observation and interviews. Observation covered Pempek Cek Yati's location, customer demographics, facilities, and activities. Interviews with the owner were transcribed for analysis, which included categorization, coding (e.g., using "CP" for company profile), and organizing data by category. The study utilized two frameworks to structure and analyze findings, guiding the drafting process.

Preliminary Study

After conducting observations and interviews, the writer obtained detailed data about Pempek Cek Yati, including its strategic location next to a highway and shopping center. The study revealed that besides various types of pempek, the restaurant also offers other dishes like Model, Tekwan, Lenggang, Otak-Otak, and beverages. The owner emphasized the affordability, absence of additional sweeteners, and use of halal and healthy ingredients in their products. Pempek Cek Yati operates daily from 09:00 to 21:00, and the owner provided valuable insights on delivery orders, enhancing the writer's ability to create compelling product drafts.

The study applied two frameworks for drafting: Oshima & Hogue's text structure (2006), focusing on opening, body, and conclusion, and Kotler & Keller's AIDA Formula (2009), which addresses Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action. Evaluating the copy through different frameworks allowed the writer to enhance effectiveness and address weaknesses, ensuring the content resonated well with the audience.

Model Development

After the writer made the product's draft, the writer developed the draft by conducting limited and wider tests to two experts in each test.

a. Limited testing

Two participants checked the copywriting to verify the content of the copywriting in Indonesia and the English Language. The experts were Ms. Dea Destriana and Ms. Pratiwi Lestari, M.Pd. First, Ms. Dea Destriana, copywriting expert, corrected the mistake of dictions, grammar, and punctuation.

b. Wider testing

In this wider testing, the writer continued to develop the video with more participants that know about video editing well. As the result, the writer accepted good feedback from the fifth of the participants, starting from the quality of the video, the back sound, and the concept. However,

the video was also corrected by them because there were some scenes in the video that need to be improved. It included the effect, the font and colour of the subtitle and additional information about contact person, writer's name and institution logo at the end of video.

The first expert was Mr. Rio Pratama the video editor and graphic designer in Trakom Course. The interview was conducted on July, 5th 2023. He said that the video was good enough. However, Mr. Rio also suggested changing the filter of two of the scenes to become brighter than before.

Final Product

The final product was made by determining which extract is belonging to AIDA Formula. After the writer revised the draft of copywriting and the video based on experts' suggestion and comments, the writer then considered the last revision became the final product. It is also because of time constraints, financial constraints, and legal considerations. After some revisions, here is the final product.

Table 1. Final Product.

<p>Opening:</p> <p>Is there really pempek with delicious taste but affordable in Palembang city? Yes, there really is!</p> <p>Body:</p> <p>Pempek Cek Yati comes with many variants of mouth-watering pempek. This culinary place is located on Simpang Poltek Street, Lebak Keranji, Palembang city and opens from 9 am to 9 pm. If we take a look, this culinary place is certainly comfortable, nice, and also suitable for eating with family or friends. Let's take a look at the menus at Pempek Cek Yati. Wow, it turns out that they sell not only variants of pempek but also many other menus, such as lenggang, models, otak-otak, tekwan, and several drinks.</p>

Here are the favorite menus that you must try! It looks appealing and appetizing. Let's try! Hmmm, it tastes good and makes you addicted! Especially if it is eaten with cuko sauce which is so delicious because it is made from “gulo batok”, the palm sugar that is originally from Palembang.

Well, the other menus here that we ordered are model and otak otak. The taste is no less delicious than the main menu! The portions are also large with very affordable prices. Don't forget! We also ordered the famous orange ice without any additional sweetener because it uses real sugar! The sweetness is just right, fresh, and makes the tongue feel pampered.

What's more, foodies don't need to worry, because all food and drinks here are halal. For those of you who want to try Pempek Cek Yati, but don't have enough time to go directly to the location, you can use the Gojek or Grab applications on the go send or grab send feature to order. It is simple, isn't it?

Closing:

So what are you waiting for? Let's try pempek and various other menus at
Pempek Cek Yati!

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The ad copy for Pempek Cek Yati follows Sukmadinata's approach in three steps: Preliminary study involves researching copywriting sources. Data collection through observation and interviews informs the initial draft based on Oshima and Hogue's text structure (2006) and Kotler & Keller's AIDA Formula (2009). In Model development, seven experts review and suggest revisions for the video copywriting, which are incorporated until final approval. The ad copy includes an opening with a compelling question, an informative body covering company profile, operational details, menu offerings, and product strengths, and a closing urging viewers

to visit. Effective video copywriting requires precise diction, clear language, and compelling calls to action for maximum impact.

The video copywriting product research is incomplete without the final stages of the research and development method. Future researchers should prioritize completing the final product and dissemination stages. Seeking feedback from users and stakeholders after uploading the video copywriting is crucial for refining and enhancing its effectiveness in advertising. Balancing concept creation, diction selection, and video editing is essential for receiving clear, actionable suggestions to improve ad copywriting for culinary purposes.

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